

Spectrophotometric study of photosensitized dechlorination of isomeric chloroanisidines

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The photosensitized dechlorination of isomeric 5-chloro-*o*-anisidine (5-C-*o*-A) and 3-chloro-*p*-anisidine (3-C-*p*-A) has been studied using methylene blue (MB) as photosensitizer in alkaline medium. The 100 W tungsten lamp was used for irradiation. The dechlorination products are identified and formation of a molecular complex between anisidine and methylene blue is observed. The effect of pH, concentration of sensitizer, substrate, intensity of light and temperature on the rate of the reaction has been studied. The quantum efficiency of the photodechlorination has been evaluated using potassium ferrioxalate actinometer. The removal of chlorine from the substrate was tested with silver nitrate. The dechlorination products of isomeric chloroanisidines have been confirmed by shift in the wavelength. The mechanism of the photodechlorination has been suggested. The rate of the reaction of the dechlorination follows the order : 5-C-*o*-A > 3-C-*p*-A.

The chlorinated aromatic compounds are hazardous for environment because of their toxic and carcinogenic effect. They have long life, chemical stability and are non-biodegradable, which have created keen interest of scientists in their degradation. The new techniques are developed for the degradation of these compounds to convert them into less toxic material. Photosensitized degradation by sun-simulated light is one of the techniques used¹.

Anisidines and their derivatives are used in the synthesis of dyes, carbolines², polyanisidines³ and antioxidant drugs⁴. The compounds show carcinogenic effect on living beings⁵⁻⁷ and also cause short-term mutagenicity⁷.

The present study reports photosensitized dechlorination of isomeric 5-chloro-*o*-anisidine and 3-chloro-*p*-anisidine in alkaline medium. Methylene blue has been used as photosensitizer which has also been used as sensitizer in a number of photochemical reactions^{8,9}.

The irradiation of the sample was carried out in sun-simulated light. The rate of the dechlorination, quantum efficiency (ϕ) and effect of different parameters on the rate of the dechlorination have been studied and a reaction mechanism has been suggested. It is observed that there is formation of a molecular complex between anisidine and methylene blue.

Results and discussion

The spectra of 5-C-*o*-A and 3-C-*p*-A were recorded in the range of 200–400 nm under the experimental condi-

tions show absorption bands at 240 nm and 237 nm corresponding to π - π^* transition and 300 nm and 307 nm correspond to n - π^* transition for 5-C-*o*-A and 3-C-*p*-A respectively. The spectra of solutions of chloroanisidines along with methylene blue (MB) after exposure show that π - π^* bands do not change while n - π^* bands have shifted from 300 nm and 307 nm to 325 nm and 355 nm for 5-C-*o*-A and 3-C-*p*-A respectively. The molar absorptivity of n - π^* bands have increased (Table 1). Without exposure the solutions containing MB do not show spectral changes.

Table 1. Experimental values of λ_{\max} and molar absorptivity of anisidines and chloroanisidines

Compd.	Experimental λ_{\max} (ϵ value)	Product λ_{\max} (ϵ value)
<i>o</i> -Anisidine	235 (8000)	235 (8000)
	300 (1125)	325 (4437)
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	232 (8775)	232 (8775)
	307 (862)	355 (4725)
5-Chloro- <i>o</i> -anisidine	240 (7800)	235 (7800)
	300 (1400)	325 (4287)
3-Chloro- <i>p</i> -anisidine	237 (8837)	232 (8837)
	307 (1237)	355 (3050)
Methylene blue	665 (3560)	—

The spectra of *o*- and *p*-anisidine (*o*-A and *p*-A) were recorded under the similar experimental conditions, show absorption bands at 235 nm and 232 nm corresponding to π - π^* transition and 300 nm and 307 nm correspond n - π^*

transition for *o*-A and *p*-A respectively. The $n-\pi^*$ bands have shifted from 300 nm and 307 nm to 325 nm and 355 nm for *o*-A and *p*-A respectively, which match with the exposed solutions of chloroanisidines. Therefore it is concluded that 5-C-*o*-A and 3-C-*p*-A are converted into *o*-A and *p*-A, when exposed to visible light in the presence of MB.

The increase in the absorbance at 325 nm and 355 nm was measured at different time interval till it becomes constant (completion of the reaction) (Table 2). It is observed that in the case of 5-C-*o*-A, the reaction goes to the completion but it is comparatively slower in the case of 3-C-*p*-A.

Table 2. Rate of photosensitized dechlorination and quantum efficiencies of chloroanisidines

[5-C-*o*-A] = [3-C-*p*-A] = 8×10^{-5} M, [MB] = 4×10^{-6} M, light intensity = 11.18×10^{-8} E/s, pH = 12, temp. = 298 K

Compd.	$k \times 10^1$ (min ⁻¹)	ϕ -Value
5-Chloro- <i>o</i> -anisidine	5.7575	1.6010
3-Chloro- <i>p</i> -anisidine	3.4540	0.8793

A plot of $2 + \log$ (absorbance) vs time was found to be straight line with a positive slope. This indicates that the reaction follows first order reaction kinetics. The rate constant of the reaction was determined by using the following expression :

$$\text{Rate constant} = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$$

Effect of pH : Methylene blue doesn't work as a photosensitizer in acidic medium for this reaction. The rate constant of the photosensitized reaction was calculated at different pH for 5-C-*o*-A and 3-C-*p*-A between 8–13 pH. It was observed that as the pH increases, the rate of the reaction increases slowly, but between 11 to 12 pH, a large increase in the rate of the reaction was observed and it became constant (Fig. 1). Therefore the pH 12 was selected for the subsequent studies.

Effect of concentration of the sensitizer : The effect of the concentration of methylene blue on the rate of the dechlorination was studied by calculating the rate constant for 5-C-*o*-A and 3-C-*p*-A using different concentrations of methylene blue in the range of 0.4×10^{-5} – 2.0×10^{-5} M. The effect of increase in the concentration of the sensitizer didn't show change in the rate of the reaction. However the rate slightly decreases at the higher concentration of the sensitizer. It appears that self deactivation of the sensitizer takes place at higher concentration.

Effect of the concentration of the substrate : The effect of the initial concentration of 5-C-*o*-A and 3-C-*p*-A on the rate of the reaction was studied in the range of 0.4×10^{-4} –

1.2×10^{-4} M, which remains constant with increase in the initial concentration of the substrate. This shows that the reaction is independent of the initial concentration of the substrate. However the rate of the dechlorination of 5-C-*o*-A is higher than 3-C-*p*-A (Table 2).

Fig. 1. Effect of pH. [5-C-*o*-A] = [3-C-*p*-A] = 8×10^{-5} M, [MB] = 4×10^{-6} M, light intensity = 11.18×10^{-8} E/s, temp. = 298 K.

Effect of light intensity : The increase of light intensity [Einstein/second (E/s)] shows positive effect and the rate of the dechlorination increases as the light intensity increases. The number of the excited molecules of the sensitizer increases with higher light intensity as the number of photons increases and corresponding rate of the reaction increases (Table 3). A linear relationship is observed between the light intensity and the rate of the reaction.

Table 3. Effect of the light intensity

[5-C-*o*-A] = [3-C-*p*-A] = 8×10^{-5} M, [MB] = 4×10^{-6} M, pH = 12, temp. = 298 K

Light intensity 10^8 I (E/s)	$k \times 10^1$ (min ⁻¹)	
	5-Chloro- <i>o</i> -anisidine	3-Chloro- <i>p</i> -anisidine
4.47	1.9345	1.1515
6.72	3.1666	2.3030
11.18	5.7575	4.6060

Effect of temperature : The effect of the variation of the temperature was studied between 298–328 K on the rate of the reaction. The rate of the reaction remains constant with the increase in the temperature in the above range. This

indicates that the rate of the reaction is independent of temperature and thermal condition does not affect the photodechlorination. The temperature independent nature of the rate of the reaction also indicates that the product formation takes place directly from the excited species without any intermediate stage¹.

ϕ -Value : The quantum efficiency was calculated by using standard potassium ferrioxalate actinometer and it was found that $\phi_{5-C-o-A} > \phi_{3-C-p-A}$ (Table 2). ϕ values were calculated for the chloroanisidines at different initial concentrations of the substrate. There is a linear relationship between the initial concentration of the substrate and ϕ value. The plot of inverse of quantum efficiency versus inverse of the initial concentration of the substrate was found to be linear with a positive slope (Fig. 2), which suggests that there is a direct product formation from the singlet-excited state and not via triplet intermediate state¹⁰.

Fig. 2. Inverse of quantum efficiency vs the inverse of [substrate] : [MB] = 4×10^{-6} M, light intensity = 11.18×10^{-8} E/s, pH = 12, temp. = 298 K.

Mechanism :

Anisidines and chloroanisidines have their λ_{\max} below 300 nm. These molecules do not absorb the visible light and they are not photodegraded directly. Methylene blue (MB) has λ_{\max} 665 nm (Table 1). The absorption of the radiation at this λ_{\max} results in the singlet-excited state of methylene blue⁹. The energy transfer from singlet-excited state of MB to isomeric chloroanisidines takes place, resulting in the ground state of MB and singlet-excited state of chloroanisidines and anisidines (Scheme 1).

The change in original spectra of isomeric *o*- and *p*-anisidines were observed after exposure along with MB. The adsorption band of π - π^* of anisidines remains unchanged, but n - π^* bands showed red shift and with increased absorptivity. The non-bonding electrons of anisidines are excited in the lower vacant orbital of MB forming a molecular complex¹¹. The molecular complex shows higher absorptivity and longer wavelength absorption at 325 nm and 355 nm for *o*- and *p*-anisidine respectively (Table 1).

Scheme 1

The excited chloroanisidine molecule simultaneously undergoes dechlorination and transfer of non-bonding electrons to MB molecule, forming a molecular complex. The molecular complex is in the ground state, which shows absorption band corresponding to the molecular complex between anisidine and MB. The absorbance of the molecular complex remains constant with time (Scheme 1).

The plot of inverse of ϕ versus inverse of initial concentration of the substrate is linear with a positive slope, which indicates that there is a direct product formation from the singlet-excited state of the substrate and not via intermediate triplet state¹⁰.

Conclusions :

Isomeric chloroanisidines undergo photosensitized dechlorination in the presence of methylene blue and visible light in alkaline medium. The spectral profiles of the exposed solution suggest that the products of the reaction are *o*- and *p*-anisidine in the case of 5-C-*o*-A and 3-C-*p*-A respectively. The molecular complex between excited state of anisidine and ground state of MB is formed.

The study of different parameters concludes that the rate of the dechlorination is dependent on light intensity and pH and is independent of temperature, initial concentration of substrate and concentration of sensitizer. ϕ value is dependent on initial concentration of substrate. The rate of reaction follows the order : 5-C-*o*-A > 3-C-*p*-A.

Experimental

All chemicals used for the experiments were of A.R. grade (Aldrich), and no further purification was done. Absolute alcohol (99%) was used after distillation. Double-distilled water was used for the dilution.

The 100 W tungsten filament light source (Philips) was used for the exposure of the sample solution. Glass water jacket was used to decrease the temperature of the solution. All spectral measurements were done on UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Spectrascan-2800-Cibacorning, England). pH of the solution was measured using pH meter (Systronics, India).

The 10^{-3} M solutions of anisidines and chloroanisidines were prepared by weighing 0.0123 g and 0.01575 g of each substrate and dissolved in the minimum volume of ethanol and made up to the mark in 100 ml volumetric flask with double-distilled water. The 10^{-3} M solution of methylene blue was prepared by weighing 0.0374 g methylene blue and dissolved in double-distilled water and made up to the mark in 100 ml volumetric flask with double-distilled water. The aliquots of the stock solution were diluted as required before use.

Four sets of the experiment were prepared by withdrawing 4 ml of 10^{-3} M solution of chloroanisidines, 10 ml of 10^{-1} M NaOH in each 50 ml volumetric flask and 2 ml of 10^{-4} M solution of methylene blue was added to two flasks and solutions of all four flasks were made up to the mark with double-distilled water. The final concentrations of chloroanisidines and methylene blue were 8.0×10^{-5} M and 4.0×10^{-6} M respectively. The measurements were carried out at pH 12.

Two flasks, one of each containing methylene blue and without methylene blue were kept in the dark for 24 h while remaining similar flasks were exposed to visible light from

100 W tungsten lamp. The course of the reaction was followed by recording the spectrum of the exposed solution with a control solution in the range of 200–400 nm against reagent blank.

The flask kept in the dark and flask exposed without sensitizer did not show any difference in the spectrum when compared to control; while the exposed flask containing sensitizer showed shift in λ_{\max} from the original spectrum. This confirms that reaction takes place only in the presence of the methylene blue on irradiation. Thus, the reaction is photosensitized dechlorination and not normal or thermal dechlorination.

The change in the absorbance was measured with 5 ml aliquot of the reaction solution at different time intervals at 325 nm in the case of 5-C-*o*-A and at 355 nm for 3-C-*p*-A for the calculation of the rate of the reaction. Free chloride was tested in the exposed solution with silver nitrate by observing white precipitate of AgCl. This was compared with control experiment run as blank without sample in which the Cl^- test was found negative. The temperature of the solution was maintained at 298 K using water jacket.

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